

Faculty Awareness and Willingness to Deposit Local Contents to Institutional Repositories in Nigeria: A Case Study

Emmanuel E. BARO (CLN)

The University Library,
Federal University Otuoke,
Bayelsa State, Nigeria

baroee@fuotuoike.edu.ng, karaperekumor@yahoo.com

Prof. Anthonia U. NWABUEZE-ECHEDOM (CLN)

Department of Library and Information Science,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nigeria.

auchedom@gmail.com

Abstract

The study investigated the awareness and willingness of faculty staff in University of Nigeria, Nsukka to deposit their research works in their university institutional repository. An online questionnaire was designed to collect data from 185 faculty members in seven departments in the Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The study found that the faculty members are aware of the benefits of depositing in IR. They are willing to submit content to the IR. They believe that the repository is a necessity for the university and their own research visibility. The faculty members agreed that factors such as poor internet connectivity, lack of technical know-how, lack of motivation from management, time-consuming, fear of plagiarism, copyright issues might hinder them from depositing documents to the IR of the university. The study recommends that university management should provide incentives for academic staff to motivate them to deposit or self-archive their locally produced contents in the IR, and that universities should provide regular training sessions to members of academic staff on how to upload local contents in IRs.

Keywords: Institutional repositories, faculty, local contents, Universities, Nigeria.

Introduction

Building an effective open access institutional repository (OAIR) collection requires the involvement of both academic staff and library staff in depositing or self-archiving locally produced contents (Mbughuni, Mtega & Malekani, 2022). The involvement of academic staff is very important because they are the ones who produce contents from their research and academic activities. This was also revealed by Musa, Shittu and Abdulkadir (2014) when they reported that the most critical issue that lies behind the success of any institutional repository is self-archiving among academic staff. The objective of OAIRs in universities is to capture and collect different publications, locally produced contents which can be accessed and used by the university community and researchers outside. Gul, Bashir and Ganaie (2020) stated that since IRs captures, preserve and disseminates collective intellectual capital, it serves as a meaningful indicator of an institution's academic quality. This implies that research institutions like universities are measured by the quality of publications made available and accessible to researchers world-wide.

This locally produced contents can be monographs or peer-reviewed journal articles, as well as electronic theses or dissertations and other digital assets such as data sets, course notes, learning objects

or conference proceedings (Saulus, Mutula & Dlamini, 2017). Locally produced contents are generated or produced by academic staff and students in the university from their academic work. They are considered to be very important as it provides knowledge to the university community, satisfies local information needs, enhances self-reliance, enable intra and extra digital divide, enhances easy and free community access to information, and gives the academic community an identity as it mirrors real-life situations and operations (Saulus, Mutula & Dlamini, 2017). For these local contents to be visible, it is important to deposit them in OAIRs. Institutional repositories make articles visible and increase the chances for use by other scholars and exchange ideas among similar disciplines (Nghah, 2010). Depositing a paper in the institutional repository is one way of increasing paper's visibility (Mbughuni, Mtega & Malekani, 2022). Commonly cited benefits of using an institutional repository are to increase the visibility and citation impact of the institution's scholarship (Tate, 2010).

Depositing locally produced contents in OAIRs in this context can be defined as the process whereby library or academic staff upload locally produced contents into the university's OAIRs. In the past, it was librarians who normally deposited contents in university OAIRs on behalf of the authors because they were the custodians of the OAIRs (Baro, Tralagba & Ebiagbe, 2018). Nowadays, library staff alone cannot deposit all the contents created by university communities because it is difficult to know what has been created by academic staff or researchers. The engagement of academic staff in depositing locally produced contents in OAIRs is therefore very important. Engagement can be defined as the way in which academic staff are involved in the process of depositing locally produced contents in the university's OAIR by either willingly giving their work to be deposited or self-archiving without the help of a librarian (Baro, Tralagba & Ebiagbe, 2018).

Several studies have reported on the low content building through self-archiving in OAIRs (Rehman, Hashmi & Jabbar, 2019; Baro, Tralagba & Ebiagbe, 2018; Mbughuni, Mtega & Malekani, 2022). Even though OAIRs provide room to deposit, store and disseminate locally produced contents, faculty members are reluctant to engage themselves by self-archiving or depositing their local contents in IRs (Mbughuni, Mtega & Malekani, 2022). Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the extent to which academic staff of the Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria engage in willingly depositing their locally produced contents to the IR.

Research questions

1. To what extent are academic staff in University of Nigeria, Nsukka aware of the IR developed in the university?
2. What type of locally produced contents are they willing to deposit to the IR?
3. What are the perceived benefits of depositing contents to the IR?
4. What are the challenges that might likely hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR.

Literature Review

Level of faculty awareness of the existence of IR in the universities.

Worldwide, OAIRs are growing very quickly, but some faculty members in universities do not know of their existence (Rehman, Hashmi & Jabbar, 2019). Awareness of academic staff about the existence of the IR in their university and the interest to deposit or self-archive locally produced contents in the OAIR is very important in the academic arena. Because, depositing contents into the IR increases the amount of contents available in the OAIR, also provides sufficient information resources for the academic community, and decreases the costs of buying information resources such as books and journals, which are expensive (Poynder 2016). IRs also provides full-text scholarly publications that are free from copyright and licensing restrictions (Poynder, 2016). Generally, the depositing of locally produced contents in an institutional repository provides a diversity of information for the community within and outside the institution cheaply and without restrictions (Jain, 2013). For example, Dutta and Paul (2014) studied faculty members of University of Calcutta awareness of institutional repository-related issues and found that most faculty members lack the awareness and does not even realize the need to deposit in IR of their institution.

Omeluzor (2014) studied institutional repository (IR) awareness and willingness of faculty staff to deposit research work in Nigerian universities and found that despite benefiting from IRs, findings reveal that 88% and 96% of the respondents from private and public universities have not deposited any publication in IR. The study recommended that awareness of IR in institutions of higher learning must be prioritized and that faculty staff should be encouraged to contribute to IR project as a means of increasing their relevance, visibility and ranking of their affiliated university. Similarly, the study by Aghwotu and Ebiagbe, (2016) revealed that despite efforts by universities to establish OAIRs, there are some academic staff who are not still aware of the existence of OAIRs in their universities. While, Baro, Tralagba and Ebiagbe, (2018) studied knowledge and use of self-archiving options among academic librarians working in universities in Africa and found that the academic librarians actually upload papers to self-archiving platforms such as institutional repository, ResearchGate, academia.edu and personal websites/ servers. They reported that author self-archiving is promising to increase visibility of articles with clearly perceived benefits of sharing scholarly output.

Willingness of faculty members to deposit in IRs

Despite the fact that some academic staff are aware of the presences of OAIRs in their universities, the amount of contents deposited in OAIRs is low, especially in Tanzania (Mnzava & Chirwa, 2018). Regarding willingness of faculty to deposit their post-published articles in IR, the study by Omeluzor (2014) shows that 78% and 75% of the respondents in private and public universities in Nigeria are willing to deposit their post published research work into IR. Similarly, the findings of Dutta and Paul (2014) also

indicates that majority of the faculty members in their study were ready to contribute their post-published articles in IR.

Mbughuni, Mtega and Malekani (2022) explored academic staff engagement in depositing locally produced research contents in open access institutional repositories in Tanzania and found that 92.5% of the respondents were aware of the presence of open access institutional repositories and 46.2% of the respondents had self-archived their academic work in open access institutional repositories. Poynder (2016) noted that "...author self-archiving has remained a minority sport, with researchers reluctant to take on the task of depositing their papers in their institutional repository. Where deposit does take place, it is invariably hard-pressed intermediaries who do the work" (p.12). Self-archiving is defined as storing the scientific research outputs in researchers' own Web pages/websites, organizational websites or institutional repositories (Erturk & Sengul, 2012). Baro, Tralagba and Ebiagbe, (2018)'s study also revealed that almost half of the academic librarians show their willingness to upload their paper to self-archiving options if mandated by funding body or institution.

Benefits of depositing contents to IRs

On the benefits of depositing in IRs, Sharma, Meichieo and Saha, (2008) reported that IR increases visibility, reflects a high quality of scholarship; demonstrates value that can translate into tangible benefits including the funding from public and private sources that drives in part from an institution status and reputation. It means that ranking and recognition of academic institution is hinged on their research publication and visibility to the outer world. Despite the good number of OAIRs that have been established and benefit from the depositing or self-archiving of locally produced contents, there are still challenges involved in self-archiving by academic staff. Most academic staff do not engage in self-archiving or give their academic work to be deposited in university OAIRs (Aghwotu & Ebiagbe, 2016; Dutta and Paul, 2014). Abuabdallah (2014) in his study identified accessibility, publicity, academic rewards and professional recognition, and sharing scientific knowledge as some of the benefits of depositing contents to IRs. Similarly, the results from Baro, Tralagba and Ebiagbe, (2018)'s study show that factors such as increase exposure of one's previously published work, provides exposure for works not previously published (e.g. seminar papers), broadens the dissemination of academic research generally and increases one's institutions' visibility were among the options the academic librarians rated as very important factors that motivate them to contribute their scholarly output to the self-archiving options.

Challenges that might likely hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR.

Studies have found that there are several challenges with regard to depositing or self-archiving locally produced contents in OAIRs, such as lack of awareness of the process, time limitations, lack of technical skills, an unstable network and electricity problems (Mnzava & Chirwa, 2018; Omeluzor, 2014). Yang, Ye & Li, (2015) identified copyright issues, time and effort as factors that frustrate faculty

contributions through self-archiving to OAIRs. Similarly, Saini (2018) shared the Nigerian experience and found that lack of interest, fear of copyright violation and plagiarism frustrate the academic staff from depositing to IRs. While, Singso, Sevukan and Murugaiyan (2015) reported that the lack of a good understanding of publishers' licensing policy was a challenge that faced academic staff and librarians when self-archiving.

Methodology

The study adopted online method to collect data from faculty members of Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. One criterion for the selection of the University of Nsukka was that the university is among the universities that have developed OAIR, and is registered in the Open Directory of Open Access Institutional Repository (OpenDOAR).

The link to the online questionnaire was forwarded to the academic staff of seven departments in Faculty of Education e-mail addresses. The e-mail addresses were collected from the university website. Data collection started January 2023 and ended in March, 2023. The online questionnaire was forwarded to 294 respondents in seven departments under faculty of education. To raise the response rate, the respondents were reminded twice in an e-mail to respond to the online questionnaire.

In total, 185 respondents responded to the online questionnaire with respond rate of 62.9 per cent. The data was analyzed and results presented in tables and chart.

Results

Seven out of the either departments in the Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria (UNN) responded to the study with total number of 185 respondents. Out the number, 63 (34.1%) are Lecturer I, 50 (27.0%) are Associate Professors, 41 (22.2%) are Lecturer II, 22 (11.9%) are Professors, and 9 (4.9%) are Assistant Lecturers.

Table 1: Number of respondents from the departments.

Departments	No of respondents
Adult education	22
Arts education	30
Educational Foundation	45
Science education	27
Library and information science	7
Health and Physical Education	21
Social science education	33
Total	185

Level of awareness of the existence of IR in the university.

Respondents were requested to state whether or not they were aware of the existence of the UNN IR. As shown in Table 2, the majority (131: 69.7%) of the respondents indicated that they were aware, while 54(30.3%) indicated that they were not aware.

Table 2: Level of awareness of the existence of IR in the university.

Level of awareness	Aware	Not aware	Total no.
Adult education	16 (69.2%)	6(30.8%)	22
Arts education	22(71%)	8 (28.6%)	30
Educational Foundation	31(72.7%)	14(27.3%)	45
Science education	18(75%)	9(25%)	27
Library and information science	6(84.6%)	1 (1.4%)	7
Health and Physical Education	15 (62.5%)	6(37.5%)	21
Social science education	23(73.3%)	10(26.7%)	33
Total	131(69.7%)	54(30.3%)	185

Type of local contents respondents are willing to deposit in the IR

Respondents were asked to indicate the type of local contents they are willing to deposit in the IR. Results in Figure 1 shows that a majority of the respondents (177: 95.7%), were willing to share theses and dissertations, followed by 134 (72.4%) respondents who indicated their willingness to share their journal articles (pre-print or post-print), and more than half (101: 54.6%) of the respondents indicated that they are willing to deposit conference/workshop papers and presentations. Regarding book chapters, 81 (43.8%) respondents indicated they are willing to share their book chapters, 79 (42.7%) indicated that they are willing to deposit lecture notes to the IR, and 41 (22.1%) indicated they would deposit technical reports to the IR.

Perceived benefits of depositing contents to the IR

Respondents were asked to rate the level they agree or disagree with the statements regarding their perceived benefits of depositing contents to the IR. The majority (153: 82.7%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that depositing their research papers on the IR will make them visible globally. Also, the majority (210: 91.8%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that depositing their research papers on the IR will attract more citations. The majority (172: 93%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree

that depositing on the IR will increase usage of their work. All (185: 100%) the respondents strongly agree and agree that the IR allows for global access to scholarly literature. The majority (164: 88.7%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that depositing to the IR enables researchers outside to access literature more easily (Table 3).

Table 3: Perceived benefits of depositing contents to the IR

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Depositing my research papers on the IR will make me visible globally.	88 (47.6%)	65 (35.1%)	32 (17.3%)	-
Depositing my research papers on the IR will attract more citations.	177 (74.0%)	33 (17.8%)	15 (8.1%)	-
Depositing on the IR will increase usage of my work	116 (62.7%)	56 (30.3%)	13 (7.0%)	-
The IR allows for global access to scholarly literature	166 (89.7%)	19 (10.3%)	-	-
The IR enables researchers to access literature more easily	93 (50.3%)	71 (38.4%)	21 (11.4%)	-

Challenges that might likely hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR.

Respondents were asked to rate the level they agree or disagree with the statements regarding the challenges that might hinder them from depositing their work to the IR. Results in Table 4 shows that 154 (83.2%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree with the statement that poor Internet connectivity might likely hinder them from depositing their work to the IR. The majority (162: 85.4%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree with the statement that lack of technical know-how (that is skills on how to upload) might hinder them from depositing their work to the IR. The majority (160: 86.5%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree with the statement that lack of motivation from management might discourage them from depositing their work to the IR. The majority (155: 83.7%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that depositing their work to the IR is time-consuming. Also, the majority (177: 95.7%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that fear of plagiarism might hinder them from depositing their work to the IR. The majority (138: 74.5%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree that copyright issues might hinder them from depositing their work to the IR.

Table 4: Challenges that might likely hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR

Challenges	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Poor Internet connectivity	102 (55.1%)	52 (28.1%)	31 (16.8%)	-
Lack of technical know-how	92 (49.7%)	66 (35.7%)	27 (14.6%)	-
Lack of motivation from management	111 (60%)	49 (26.5%)	12 (6.5%)	13 (7.0%)
Time-consuming	85 (45.9%)	70 (37.8%)	30 (16.2%)	-
Fear of plagiarism	109 (58.9%)	68 (36.8%)	8 (4.3%)	-
Copyright issues	99 (53.5%)	39 (21.0%)	22 (11.9%)	25 (13.5%)

Discussion of findings

Level of awareness of the existence of IR in the university.

Awareness was considered one of the important aspects that evoke development, and a lack of it was perceived to prevent academics from using the IR. The study revealed that the majority of the faculty members are aware of the existence of the IR in the university. This implies that there has been an improvement in academic faculty awareness of the presence of IRs. This finding is contrary to the earlier findings by Omeluzor (2014) who reported that reasons why most contributors especially faculty members fail to deposit their intellectual contents may be attributed to lack of awareness.

Type of local contents faculty are willing to deposit to the IR

A question requiring multi-responses was asked to determine the content types that respondents were willing to deposit in the IR. The present study found that dissertations and theses, journal articles, and conference/workshop papers and presentations were the most mentioned categories of documents they were willing to deposit in the IRs. This implies that these documents are deposited more often and preferable for most academic staff. This is supported by Nunda and Elia's (2019) research, which found that the preferred categories deposited in OAIRs were theses or dissertations, journal articles, conference papers and seminar papers. It is imperative for Nigerian scholars to self-archive their research works published as this will make works from Nigeria to be accessible globally. This in other words, will make authors from Nigeria to be visible with the opportunity of collaborating and sharing ideas with authors from the developed world.

Perceived benefits of depositing contents to the IR

From the analysis, it was found that faculty members depositing their research papers on the IR will make them visible globally, it will attract more citations, increase usage of their work, allows for global access to scholarly literature, and IR enables researchers outside to access literature more easily were seen as the perceived benefits of depositing their works to the IR. This may be why, Crow (2002) called for producers of primary research and academic institutions to take interest to capture and preserve the intellectual output of their faculty, staff, and students and deposit same in IR to support the university community.

Challenges that might hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR.

Regarding challenges that might hinder the academic staff from depositing their work to the IR. The study found that poor Internet connectivity, lack of technical know-how, lack of motivation from management, time-consuming, fear of plagiarism, copyright issues might hinder them from depositing documents to the IR of the university. These are common challenges that hinder the depositing of local contents in OAIRs in most universities across Africa, especially in Nigeria. For example, Kodua-Ntim and Fombad (2020) conducted research on the strategies for the use of open access institutional repositories in Africa and found that there is a slow uptake of institutional repositories due to inadequate advocacy,

intellectual property rights and copyright issues, ICT connectivity and infrastructure, the institutional culture, OAIR policies, limited awareness of OAIR, inadequate funding of OAIRs, lack of reward systems and incentives, and inefficient power supply.

To improve acceptance and use of the IR, the university needed to introduce a reward system to lure academics who were not self-archiving, and at the same time motivate those self-archiving to continue uploading their scholarly work on the IR. Moral and/or financial support, acknowledging and recognizing academics that self-archive are other alternatives necessary to foster the development of the repository.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis, the study found that the academic staff are aware of the benefits of depositing in IRs. They are willing to submit contents to the IR. They believe that the repository is a necessity for the university and their own research visibility. Meanwhile, the faculty members agreed that factors such as poor internet connectivity, lack of technical know-how, lack of motivation from management, time-consuming, fear of plagiarism, copyright issues might hinder them from depositing documents to the IR of the university. The self-archiving of locally produced contents in OAIRs provides knowledge to the university community, satisfies local information needs, enhances free community access to content, and increases the visibility of the university. Low engagement in self-archiving locally of produced contents will lead to a lack of content and low university visibility.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following are recommended:

- Since respondents reported low motivation from university management, universities should provide incentives for academic staff who self-archive their locally produced contents in OAIRs.
- Universities should make sure that they provide academic staff with enough research funds to motivate them to deposit their research works to the IR.
- Universities and other academic organizations should provide regular training sessions to members of academic staff on how to upload local content in OAIRs.

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